

The Time-varying Impact of Monetary Policy on Asset Prices

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Abstract

This paper investigates the time-varying impact of U.S. monetary policy shocks on asset prices. The monetary policy shock is identified using robust sign restrictions in a time-varying factor-augmented VAR (TVP-FAVAR). Time variations are found in both the variance of policy shocks and transmission to asset prices. The relative importance of monetary policy shocks rise significantly over time although the shock size of monetary policy shocks has declined in the sample. In terms of transmission mechanism, asset prices are more responsive in the latter part of the sample (post-1984Q1) when normalizing the shock size. We also document the effects of monetary policy on asset prices are significantly larger for recessionary periods. Finally, the paper also identifies the role of demand and supply shocks in determining the movements of asset prices.

Keywords: Monetary policy; Asset prices; Time-varying; Structural FAVAR; Sign restrictions

JEL Classification Numbers: E44, E52, XY.

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1 Introduction

The recent financial crisis of 2008-2009 has seen a dramatic decline in asset prices and housing prices. Following the decline of the asset prices was the plummet of the real economy (Gorton and Metrick, 2012[22]). At the same time, unprecedented interventions of monetary policy and fiscal policy stepped in. For example, multiple rounds of QE were exerted during and after the period. This generated the interest in academia about whether the central bank should respond to the asset price deviation from fundamentals, which is actually a debate existing for a long time. The presumption for the concern is that the asset prices could be affected effectively by the monetary policy.

Against this background, we ask how effects of monetary policy on asset prices evolve over time. Monetary policy could be more effective if the asset prices are more responsive, via Q-theory channel or balance sheet channel (Ellis et al., 2014 [20] and Bernanke and Gertler, 1989 [4]). On the other hand, the less reaction of asset prices will weaken the stance of 'lean against the wind' taken by the central bank. In view of this, this paper is about to thoroughly investigate the time-varying effects of the monetary policy on a wide range of asset prices in a unified framework.

The advantages of employing a time-varying factor-augmented VAR (TVP-FAVAR) are at least threefold. First, it takes into account the structural changes to estimate the effects of monetary policy shocks on asset prices. As Canova and Pérez-Forero (2015)[13] pointed out, constant coefficients VAR or FAVAR could indicate misleading structural relationships if the structure is changing over time. Second, including large-scale data series in the model could reduce the estimated bias caused by the mismatch between the large information set used by economic agents (e.g. central banks and private agents) and the information set spanned by the variables in the small-scale VAR (Bernanke et al., 2005[5]). Third, due to the characteristic of the data-rich environment in a factor model, we can investigate the effects of monetary policy on a wide range of asset prices without many concerns on the dimensionality problem.

Another salient feature of our method to differentiate from extant literature is that we use sign restrictions to identify the monetary policy shocks and/or other macro shocks. It is important to allow the simultaneity between the monetary policy and asset prices (Bjørnland and Leitemo, 2009[9]). Instead of using Cholesky identification scheme¹, which by assumption exclude the potential interdependence between the monetary policy and asset prices, we employ sign restrictions to identify the monetary policy shocks.

We estimate our model on quarterly US data covering the period 1960Q1-2017Q2. Our main finding is that the responsiveness of asset prices to the monetary policy shocks exhibits time-variations over time. In particular, the size of monetary policy shocks has seen a significant decline during the Great Moderation and this is consistent with the existing literature investigating the monetary policy in a time-varying setting (Primiceri, 2005[39]). In the meanwhile, we provide the evidence that the relative importance of monetary policy shocks increase over time and monetary policy shocks only account for a non-negligible fraction of movements in asset prices in recent times. This contrasts the findings associated with the role of monetary policy in real variables². In terms of the time-varying transmission mechanism, we find that the asset prices are more responsive to the monetary policy shocks in the latter part of the sample (post-1984Q1) and when the economy experience recession or financial distress. These findings are more likely to support the balance sheet channel and the expectation channel of the monetary policy (Mishkin, 2001 [33] and Boivin et al., 2010 [10]).

Apart from the effects of the monetary policy shocks, the model additionally allows us to investigate how the demand and supply shocks affect asset prices over time. We find the effects of demand shocks on all asset prices, except the stock prices and government bond yield, significantly increase recently while the reactions to the supply shocks incline to be larger during the sample. In terms of relative importance of shocks, the supply shocks are

¹Extant literature, using Cholesky identification scheme to identify monetary policy shock in asset price setting, includes Galí and Gambetti (2015) [21] and Paul (2017)[37].

²For instance, Liu et al. (2017) documents that the monetary policy plays the relatively less important role than other shocks in explaining the movements of unemployment rate.

becoming the main shock to drive the movements in asset prices.

Our paper could also potentially contribute to the literature regarding the sign restriction, starting with Uhlig (2005) [46]. Researchers criticize the ambiguity effects of contractionary monetary policy on output using sign restriction³. By employing sign restrictions in a TVP-FAVAR framework in a data-rich environment, we might potentially find the negative (conventional) effects of monetary policy on output by reducing the possible bias.

This paper proceeds as follows: In Section 2 I relate the paper to the extant literature and discuss our contributions. In Section 3 we present the data and Section 4 introduces the econometric methodology and lay out the estimation approach of the model. Section 5 presents the time-varying effects of monetary policy on the asset prices. In Section 6, we provide the sensitivity analysis to the mains results of the paper. Section 7 summarizes the main results and concludes.

2 Related literature

Bernanke and Kuttner (2005) [7] decomposed the policy action into anticipated changes and unanticipated changes and concluded that only unanticipated changes could affect asset prices. Rigobon and Sack (2003) [41] use what they call identification through heteroskedasticity, implemented by GMM or IV method. But these literature could hardly capture the dynamics of asset prices in reaction to unanticipated monetary policy change, not mentioned to provide insights on the time-varying effects that the monetary policy could potentially have.

Along the line of VAR, early literature uses recursive identification scheme to identify the effects monetary shock on asset prices. Examples are Rapach(2001) [40], Neri (2004) [35], Patelis (1997) [36] and Thorbecke (1997) [45]. Bjørnland and Leitemo(2009) [9] firstly doubt the effectiveness of employing the recursive method which, by assumption, exclude the

³As Arias et al. (2015) points out that the unconventional effects of monetary policy shock on output are caused by the estimated parameters incompatible with the systematic component of the monetary policy. In a time-varying framework, the problem could be potentially solved.

possibility of contemporaneous interdependence between monetary policy and asset prices. By utilizing the combination of short-run and long-run restrictions, they find large effects of monetary policy on US stock market. Lanne, Meitz, and Saikkonen (2017) [28], on the other hand, statistically reject the recursive identifying restrictions by developing a non-Gaussian SVAR.

The macroeconomic effects of monetary policy, since Cogley and Sargent(2005) [18], Primiceri (2005) [39] and Sims and Zha(2006) [43], have received considerable attention in a TVP-VAR framework. Researchers notice the possible changes in monetary policy transmission mechanism and/or the variance of exogenous shock over time(or both). Assuming same behavioral relationships in asset markets for a whole sample period is misleading and might result in biased estimates. In this circumstance, constant coefficients structural VAR may not be appropriate(Canova and Pérez-Forero, 2015 [13]). Boivin et al. (2010) [10] also argue that split estimation strategy could cause conflicting evidence and therefore advocates time-varying coefficients VAR to capture more complex monetary transmission mechanism. To our surprise, such effects on financial activities, in particular on the stock market and house market, have not been thoroughly investigated in a time-varying structural VAR. Galí and Gambetti (2015) [21] is an exception. They study the effects of monetary policy on stock market bubbles in a framework of TVP-VAR with recursive identification which shares the weakness we mentioned above. Instead of using recursive identification scheme, our paper employs robust sign restrictions which allows the simultaneity between asset prices and the monetary policy.

More recently, Priot et al. (2016) [38] and investigate the effects of financial shocks on the economy in a time-varying VAR framework. This highlights the importance of investigating the effects of monetary policy on asset prices.

Researchers highlight the importance of including more data to identify the macroeconomic dynamics. As discussed by Bernanke et al. (2005) [5], a VAR cannot fully depict the underlying model unless the information sets can be spanned by the variables used in the

VAR. Another caveat of using small-scale VAR is pointed out by Hansen and Sargent (1991) who claim that the structural shock cannot be recovered if the information sets mismatch. Therefore, the small-scale VAR models are unlikely to correctly gauge the relationship between the structural shocks and asset prices. Having said the benefits of using time-varying and factor augmented VAR, We therefore extend Bernanke et al. (2005) [5] by allowing for time variations in VAR coefficients and for stochastic volatility (henceforth TVP-FAVAR). Our paper contributes the extant literature by quantifying the time-varying impact of monetary policy on asset prices in a TVP-FAVAR.

3 Data description

The TVP-FAVAR is estimated with US quarterly data set from 1960:Q1-2017:Q2 (1960:Q1–1970:Q1 is the training sample). The data set consists of 119 macroeconomic data series, covering the real activities of US, such as real GDP, industrial production and household consumption, various price measure including consumer price index and producer price index, as well as the asset data sets including house price, bond yields, exchange rate and stock price index. The Federal Funds Rate is also included in the model as the monetary policy instrument controlled by the central bank. Since the Federal Funds Rate reached the zero lower bound in December 2008, we use Wu-Xia Shadow Federal Funds Rate (Wu and Xia, 2016)[49] instead for sample period 2008Q4-2015Q4⁴. The S&P 500 indexes are gathered from CRSP while the house prices are taken from Robert J. Shiller’s webpage. Original data series with monthly frequency are converted to quarterly frequency by averaging the monthly data over the quarter. We transformed all the data series to be approximately stationary.

⁴The Federal Reserve Bank started hiking the Federal Funds Rate from December 16, 2015. The monthly Wu-Xia Shadow Federal Funds Rate is averaged to get the quarterly frequency.

4 Econometric model

We begin by laying out the framework of the time-varying factor-augmented VAR and then briefly describe the prior and sampling strategy. Later in this section, we illustrate our identification scheme and show the advantage of employing sign restriction by simulating a DSGE model.

4.1 The TVP-FAVAR model

Bernanke et al. (2005)[5] explicitly recognize the advantage for additional information in an econometric model. In line with the specification in their paper, we model the US economy by using a FAVAR model specified as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{1,t} \\ \vdots \\ x_{N,t} \\ R_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda^{11} & \dots & \lambda^{K1} & \psi^{11} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \lambda^{1N} & \dots & \lambda^{KN} & \psi^{1N} \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_t^1 \\ \vdots \\ f_t^K \\ R_t \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e_{1,t} \\ \vdots \\ e_{N,t} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $X_t = (x_{1,t}, \dots, x_{N,t})$ represents a panel data set that includes US macroeconomic time series, $f_t^1, f_t^2, \dots, f_t^K$ are K latent factors designed to reduce the dimensionality while maintain the core information of the data, and R_t is the federal fund rate, the 'observed factor' as in Bernanke et al. (2005) [5]. The error term, $e_t = (e_{1,t}, \dots, e_{N,t})$, is assumed to follow Normal distribution with mean being 0 and variance covariance matrix being diagonal. The specified loading structure allows the contemporaneous reaction of variables to the federal funds rate, which is particular important in our setting to deal with the simultaneity between the asset prices and monetary policy.

In pioneering papers, Primiceri (2005) [39], Cogley and Sargent (2005) [18], Nakajima (2011) [34], and Canova and Pérez-Forero(2015) [13] propose a time-varying VAR framework and spur researchers to model time-variations in the economy. we model the behavior of real

GDP, GDP deflator inflation, house price, stock price and federal funds rate as a VAR with time-varying parameter and stochastic volatility⁵. The model allows us to not only uncover the time variation in the response of different variables to identified shocks but also capture changes over time in individual shocks and simultaneous relations among variables. In particular, we consider the following TVP-VAR model:

$$Y_t = c_t + B_{1,t}Y_{t-1} + \dots + B_{p,t}Y_{t-p} + u_t; \quad t = 1, \dots, T \quad (2)$$

where $Y_t = (f_t^1, f_t^2, \dots, f_t^K, R_t)$, including K latent factors, is an $K + 1$ dimensional vector, c_t is an $(m \times 1)$ vector of intercepts, $B_{1,t}, \dots, B_{p,t}$ are $(m \times m)$ matrices of time-varying VAR coefficients and u_t is an $(m \times 1)$ vector of reduced-form residuals that are normally distributed with a zero mean and variance covariance matrix Ω_t , with $m = K + 1$. Ω_t can be decomposed as follows:

$$\Omega_t = A_t^{-1} H_t (A_t^{-1})' \quad (3)$$

where A_t is lower triangular that gives contemporaneous relations between variables and H_t is the diagonal matrix with stochastic volatilities in the diagonal.

$$A_t = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \alpha_{21,t} & 1 & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \alpha_{m1,t} & \alpha_{m2,t} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad H_t = \begin{bmatrix} h_{1,t} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & h_{2,t} & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & h_{m,t} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Time-varying contemporaneous matrix, A_t , and stochastic variance covariance matrix, H_t , would allow the model to capture time variation in both the responses of variables and size of individual shocks. Together with time-varying coefficients, I let the data to determine whether the time variation in effects of monetary policy on asset prices is determined by

⁵There's another strand of literature, Markov-Switching VAR, which can be used to investigate the nonlinearity of relationship among variables. But it assumes the parameter drifts, at different points in time, have to occur simultaneously. See Cogley and Sargent(2005).

volatility or time varying transmission mechanism (or both).

All the coefficients of VAR are stacked into a vector, β_t , whose dimension is $m + m^2p$. Constant and the lags of Y_t are collected into a matrix Z_t . Then the model can be written as:

$$Y_t = Z_t' \beta_t + A_t^{-1} H_t \epsilon_t \quad (5)$$

It is clear that from equation (4) that the transmission of structural shock is governed by time-varying coefficients, β_t , and contemporaneous relations among variables, A_t . Following Primiceri(2005), we assume that time-varying parameters are driven by random walk as follows:

$$\beta_t = \beta_{t-1} + \mu_t, \quad \mu_t \sim N(0, Q) \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha_t = \alpha_{t-1} + \nu_t, \quad \nu_t \sim N(0, S) \quad (7)$$

$$\ln h_t = \ln h_{t-1} + \kappa_t, \quad \kappa_t \sim N(0, W) \quad (8)$$

where α_t contains the off-diagonal elements of A_t , collected in a row-wise way, h_t is a vector with elements in the diagonal of H_t . Random walk assumptions are consistent with extant literature to reduce the degree of parameterization. We also impose restrictions on the coefficient parameters such that the system is stationary.⁶ S are assumed as a block matrix with each block corresponding to a row in A_t matrix. Collecting structural shock and innovation terms of equation (5), (6) and (7) into a vector, we assume it is normally distributed:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_t \\ \mu_t \\ \nu_t \\ \kappa_t \end{bmatrix} \sim N(0, V), \quad V = \begin{bmatrix} I_m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Q & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & W \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

⁶The reason to restrict the coefficients to be stationary is, as Cogley and Sargent(2005) [18] point out, that the stationarities reflect the belief that Fed conducts monetary policy in a purposeful way that won't result in the explosiveness of macroeconomics variables. Besides this, the slow-moving but continuous adjustment is consistent with the idea that economic participants exhibit the adaptive behavior in process of ongoing learning.

The priors for parameters in FAVAR equation follows Bernanke et al. (2005). In particular, we use principal components of macroeconomic data series and asset price series X_t to pin down the prior of factors while the prior of diagonal elements of the variance covariance matrix in FAVAR equation is assumed to follow an inverse gamma distribution with scale parameter being 0.01 and degrees of freedom being 1, respectively.

As for the prior of time-varying VAR, our specifications are broadly consistent with Primiceri (2005) [39] and Cogley and Sargent (2005) [18]. In particular, we use the first twelve years of data to calibrate the distributions of priors. The OLS estimates β_0 and 4 times its variance are used to calibrate the mean and variance of β_0 . In the same manner, the initial condition of θ_0 are obtained. For $\ln h_t$, we set the mean to be the standard deviations of each equation in a constant coefficient VAR and covariance matrix to be an identity matrix. For the hyperparameters, we set them to follow inverse-Wishart distributions with scale matrices being proportional to the estimated variances of OLS. The degrees of freedom for hyperparameters associated with coefficients are equal to 1 plus the dimension (K) of β_t while the degrees of freedom for stochastic volatility hyperparameters are set to be 1 plus n (dimension of I_n). To summarize, we set the prior in time-varying equation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\beta_0 &\sim N(\hat{\beta}_{ols}, 4 * V(\hat{\beta}_{ols})) \\ A_0 &\sim N(\hat{A}_{ols}, 4 * V(\hat{A}_{ols})) \\ \ln h_0 &\sim N(\ln \hat{h}_0, I_n) \\ Q &\sim IW(k_Q^2 * (1 + K) * V(\hat{\beta}_{ols}), (1 + K)) \\ W &\sim IW((k_Z^2 * I_n, n) \\ S_i &\sim IW(k_S^2 * (1 + i) * V(\hat{A}_{i,ols}), (1 + i)), \quad i = 1 \dots n - 1\end{aligned}$$

where S_i is the i -th block of contemporaneous matrix S and $\hat{A}_{i,ols}$ denotes the i -th block of OLS estimates of matrix A using the training sample. In line with Primiceri (2005) [39] and Galí and Gambetti (2015) [21], we assume $k_Q = 0.005$, $k_Z = 0.01$ and $k_S = 0.01$. The

model is estimated using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm. Details of the algorithm and convergence test could be found in the Appendix. We run 110,000 iterations and discard the first 100,000 as burn in. We save estimates every 10th draw to reduce the autocorrelation.

4.2 Monetary shock identification

As Bjørnland and Leitemo (2009) [9] and Bjørnland and Jacobsen (2013) [8] pointed out, it is important to allow simultaneous interaction between asset prices monetary policy. This view is confirmed by the theoretical model proposed by Castelnuovo and Nisticò (2010) [16] who studies the relationship between the stock market and monetary policy in a DSGE model. Lanne, Meitz, and Saikkonen (2017) [28] support this view and statistically reject the recursive identifying restrictions by developing a non-Gaussian SVAR. So using the recursive identification scheme always gives the counter-intuitive results and this therefore highlights the benefits of using sign restrictions or allowing the simultaneous relationship.

To take into account the contemporaneous interdependence between monetary policy and asset prices, we use the sign restrictions, in line with Uhlig (2005) [46], to identify the monetary policy shock. The monetary policy shock is identified by restricting the contemporaneous impulse responses of variables in X_t to an innovation in R_t . Consistent with extant literature (e.g. Ellis et al, 2014 [20] and Smets and Wouters, 2007 [44]), contractionary monetary policy shocks are assumed to decrease GDP growth rate, decrease CPI inflation and increase the nominal interest rate. By using sign restrictions, we are exempt from restricting the magnitude of response of the contemporaneous monetary shocks and therefore agnostic about the impacts of shocks, which is of advantageous over the recursive scheme employed by Bernanke et al. (2005)[5].

In addition to monetary policy shock, we also identify an expansionary demand shock, which is assumed to increase GDP growth, CPI and short-term interest rate on impact, and a contractionary supply shock, which has a negative effect on GDP growth and a positive

effect on CPI on impact⁷.

We implement our identification scheme in a way that is consistent with Rubio-Ramirez et al. (2010) [42] who design an algorithm to select impulse responses that satisfy sign restrictions by randomly drawing an orthogonal matrix. In particular, we compute the Cholesky decomposition, A_t , of the covariance matrix, Ω_t , at each time. We draw an $m \times m$ matrix from a standard normal distribution and take the QR decomposition to get a candidate of structural impact matrix, $A_{0,t} = A_t Q$. The contemporaneous impulse response of X_t can be calculated as

$$\begin{bmatrix} irf_{x_{1,t}}^0 \\ \vdots \\ irf_{x_{N,t}}^0 \\ irf_{R_t}^0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda^{11} & \dots & \lambda^{K1} & \psi^{11} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \lambda^{1N} & \dots & \lambda^{KN} & \psi^{1N} \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \times A_{0,t}$$

where $irf_{x_{i,t}}$ denotes the contemporaneous impulse response of the variable x_t to the monetary policy shock. At each point of time, we run the procedure until we find the impulse responses that satisfy the sign restrictions and store $A_{0,t}$.

To further motivate our identification scheme, we conduct a Monte Carlo experiment based on the medium-scale DSGE model developed in Liu and Mumtaz (2011)[29]. Specifically, we draw 5,200 observations and discard the first 5,000 from the calibrated model based on the parameter estimates in Liu and Mumtaz (2011)[29]⁸. Then 2,000 artificial samples of 200 observations are generated from the model. The artificial data are used to estimate a FAVAR model with two factors. The monetary policy shock is then identified by two ways: Cholesky decomposition and sign restrictions (a contractionary shock has negative effects on domestic output and inflation and positive effects on the interest rate). Figure 1 plots

⁷These restrictive assumptions are broadly consistent with extant standard macroeconomic theory, say Smets and Wouters (2007) [44], and empirical implement procedure, say Ellis et al. (2014) [20] and Liu et al. (2017) [30].

⁸The first 5,000 observations are discarded to remove the impacts of initial conditions. One needs to note that our goal is to illustrate the validity of sign restriction in the setting of FAVAR. This could be effective even we use the artificial data generated by a DSGE model not tailored for the U.S. economy.

the impulse responses estimated by FAVAR as well as the true impulse response implied by the DSGE model. The impulse responses of sign restriction, in the right panel, are closely consistent with the true impulse responses and performs substantially better than those produced by Cholesky decomposition in the left panel in which the estimated impulse responses demonstrate a substantial deviation from the true impulse responses.

Figure 1: Impulse Responses to Monetary Policy Shock, Cholesky Decomposition vs Sign Restrictions

Notes. The left and right panel show the impulse response functions within 20 quarters for Cholesky decomposition and sign restrictions, respectively. The cyan lines are the impulse response functions estimated by FAVAR using the simulated data by DSGE model in Liu and Mumtaz (2011). The blue dashed line is the median of those estimated impulse response functions while the solid black line is the true impulse response function implied by DSGE model.

5 Time-varying effects of monetary policy on asset prices

5.1 Stochastic volatility and estimated factor

The upper panel of Figure 2 shows the two estimated factors and the time-series of Federal Funds Rate. Factor 1 highly correlated with real GDP growth and the correlation is 0.71, while Factor 2 exhibits a high correlation with price measures and the correlation with CPI inflation is 0.79. In addition, Factor 2 also correlates with financial variables with a correlation with 1 year government bond yield around 0.54.

Stochastic volatility innovations can be used to capture the changing shock sizes. Figure 2 shows the posterior mean of time-varying standard deviations of errors of each transition equation⁹. It is clear that the size of shocks changed substantially over time. Our model remarkably captures the declined volatility in the post-1980 period, which is consistent with extant literature¹⁰. Notice also how the stochastic volatility of Factor 2 captures the recent financial crisis with a substantial hike in volatility in 2009.

5.2 Time-varying transmission of monetary policy

In this section, we analyze whether the effects of monetary policy on asset prices have changed over time by characterizing the time-variations in the impulse response function of a monetary policy shock. Instead of showing time-variation in each parameter of the model, we jointly capture the effects of the VAR coefficients and the contemporaneous relations between policy rate and asset prices¹¹. In a time-varying framework, the conventional impulse responses may correspond to a different magnitude shock at each point in time (Baumeister

⁹These are computed as the square root of the diagonal elements of stochastic volatility matrix H_t .

¹⁰The significant decrease in volatility has been referred to as the Great Moderation in academia, see Primiceri (2005) and Justiniano and Primiceri (2008)[24].

¹¹The transmission mechanism of monetary policy shock is jointly captured by factor loadings, the VAR coefficients and the off-diagonal parameters in A_t matrix.

Figure 2: Stochastic volatility of shocks to each transition equation

Notes. The upper panel presents the time series of Factor 1, Factor 2 and the Federal Funds Rate. The lower panel exhibits the stochastic volatility of shocks to the three equations in the TVP-FVAR.

and Peersman, 2013 [2]). We therefore normalize the impulse responses by fixing the size of monetary policy shock to be 100 base points on impact¹².

Figure 3 visualizes the impulse response functions of asset prices to a positive monetary policy shock, normalized to increase the federal funds rate by 100 basis points on impact. The left panel displays the median impulse responses of asset prices over time. The middle two panels show impulse response difference in 1975Q1 and 2008Q1 as two representative periods

¹²In a time-varying framework, the coefficients could drift during the horizon of the impulse response functions. As in Koop et al. (1996)[26], we define the impulse response function of Y_t in transition equation as the difference between the conditional expectations: $E(Y_{t+j}|\Omega_{t+j}, \mu_t) - E(Y_{t+j}|\Omega_{t+j})$, where Ω_t denotes all the parameters and hyperparameters of the VAR and μ_t is the structural shock hitting the economy. The conditional expectations are calculated through Monte Carlo integration.

of sample¹³. The last column portraits the joint distribution of impact impulse responses for 1975Q1 and 2008Q1, as in Cogley et al. (2010)[17], to shed light on the relative importance of time variation in impulse responses of asset prices to a monetary policy shock. Evidence of systematic change of impulse response over time emerges if the joint distribution moves away from the 45 degree line.

The first row of Figure 3 plots the impulse responses of equity prices to an unanticipated positive monetary policy shock. With our identification scheme, we find that the impulse responses of stock prices have large mass below the zero line¹⁴. This is consistent with the prediction of the orthodox theory. However, the contemporaneous effects of monetary policy on stock prices exhibit insignificance for the two representative time periods. This chimes with Uhrin and Herwartz (2016) [47] who also finds insignificant responses of stock prices to a contractionary monetary policy shock in a constant VAR using sign restrictions. In terms of magnitude of effects over time, the effects on stock prices seem to be relatively stable across the time periods. The last column indicates that the joint distribution of impulse responses are symmetric across the 45 degree line providing evidence that the stable reaction of stock prices in recent times relative to the earlier part of the sample is a salient feature.

The impulse responses of 10-year government yield are reported in the third row. The hike in short-term interest rate tends to increase long-term interest rate explaining the prediction of expectation theory of term structure model. As in Ellis et al. (2013), the long-term yield could be a proxy measure of the inflation expectation. In terms of time-variations over sample period, shifts of joint distribution above the 45 degree line indicates that the responsiveness of inflation expectation is stronger in recent times and therefore provides evidence that the monetary policy is more effective regarding the expectation management which is the primary responsibility of a monetary authority, as claimed by Woodford (2003) [48].

¹³We also compare three representative periods, 1975:Q1, 1983:Q3 and 1996:Q1, as in Primiceri (2005) [39] and Korobilis (2013) [27], to represent the chairmanships of Burns, Volcker and Greenspan. The results are not displayed for brevity.

¹⁴In robustness check, alternative identification scheme supports the positive response of stock prices.

The second row of Figure 3 presents the impulse responses of house price to positive monetary policy shock. The monetary policy negatively affects house price and the effects are significantly in the sense that the 68% highest posterior density interval lies below the zero line. The effects of monetary policy, as indicated by impulse response, in 2008Q1 are twice larger than in 1975Q1. In the last column, most of probability mass points lies below the 45 degree line demonstrating apparent time variations over time. Combined with the evidence about the larger responsiveness in long-run expectation, our findings attest Case and Shiller (2003)[15] who argues that the expectations play an important role on the user costs and decision about housing spending.

The last two rows exhibits the impulse responses of nominal effective exchange rate (NEER) of US dollar and oil prices to a positive monetary policy shock. The positive response of NEER is consistent with the declining general price level (PPP) and increased short-term interest rate as indicated by interest rate parity theory while the negative responses of oil prices are mainly due to the fact that the crude oil is denominated by US dollar. Regarding the changes in magnitude over time, a similar pattern is observed, that is larger responsiveness to an unanticipated monetary disturbance in recent times.

Figure 3: Impulse Responses of Asset Prices to a Monetary Policy Shock

Notes. The left panel is the median impulse response of asset prices within 20 quarters across sample period. The middle two panels present the impulse response for two representative period, 1975Q1 and 2008 Q1, respectively. The right panel shows the joint distribution of impulse responses on impact along with 45 degree line.

Figure 4: Impulse responses of Asset Prices Over Two Sample Periods

Notes. The left panel presents impulse responses of asset prices to a contractionary monetary policy shock in the pre-1979Q3 period while the middle panel shows the impulse responses in the post-1984Q1 period. The right panel calculated the difference in impulse responses

5.3 Time-varying impacts over two sample periods

Above section present the time variations of effects of monetary policy for two representative periods under different chairmanships. This section instead computes impulse responses of asset prices to a contractionary monetary policy for pre-1979Q3 period, post-1984Q1 period and the difference of two periods. We choose those two cutoff points of time since numerous changes in government regulations and in the conduct of monetary policy occurred in the late 1970s and early 1980s. The results are reported in Figure 4. Overall the results

suggest that the effects of monetary policy on assets are greater in the post-1984Q1 period than in the pre-1979Q3 period, as indicated by the significance of difference in impulse responses in the right panel.

During our sample period, numerous regulatory changes or government interventions have been occurring. In the first part of the sample period (pre-1979Q3), the U.S. government helped introduce savings and loans associations mainly focusing on providing mortgages. The deposits interest rates, despite allowing 0.25 percent higher than commercial banks, are upper bounded by pricing ceiling under Regulation Q. In the latter sample period, Regulation Q was removed gradually (Mccarthy and Peach, 2002 [32]). If this is the main reason for the time-varying responsiveness of asset prices, then the magnitude of impulse responses should be greater in the pre-1979Q3 period since the tightening monetary policy would cause the depositors to withdraw the deposits from savings and loans associations due to the deposit rate ceilings, which would, in turn, cause a large contraction in mortgage credit and therefore a lower housing price. Our results indicate that this is not the case.

One possible explanation can be associated with the balance sheet channel (Mishkin, 2001 [33]) which suggests that the monetary policy can affect the firm's performance and the economy by affecting the balance sheets of firms and consumers. Rising interest rates lead to increase firm's interest payments which lower firm's cash flow. Lowering cash flow not only places downward pressures on stock prices but also increases problems with asymmetric information in debt financing which in turn increases external finance premium (Bernanke and Gertler, 1989 [3]). This can further limit the access to the credit and therefore deteriorate the firm's performance. The first row of Figure 5 indicates that impulse of responses of firm's credit supply, proxied by Commercial & Industrial Loans Outstanding, are greater during the latter sample period. This is consistent with a stronger balance sheet channel. We also use alternative measures of external finance premium, AAA spread and BAA spread¹⁵, to further examine how the balance sheet channel may change over time. The results in the

¹⁵AAA (BAA) spread is defined as the difference between the yield on AAA (BAA) corporate bonds and federal funds rate.

third and fourth row indicate that the magnitude of impulse responses are slightly greater in the post-1984Q1 period which exhibits evidence that the balance sheet channel becomes more important in the latter sample period. In addition, the changes in impulse responses of consumer credit to monetary policy shocks are reported in the second row of Figure 5. This suggests that the balance sheet channel of monetary policy also affects households, which is in line with Iacoviello (2005) [23] who argues that the problems with asymmetric information problem, thereby influencing the credit access, also apply to housing and household expenditures.

Another possible reason can be attributed to the change in the behavior of monetary policy. As Woodford (2003) [48] emphasized, “management of expectation” should be the primary transmission channel of monetary policy. Shifts in the conduct of the monetary policy can influence how the economy and asset prices respond to monetary policy. Asset prices could be directly impacted by the expected path of short-term interest rates. For instance, forward guidance on a more persistent increase in short-term interest could have larger effects on long-term interest rates than a less persistent rise, as implied by the expectation hypothesis of the term structure model. To investigate the role of changing expectation channel, we therefore directly examine the time-varying responsiveness of a measure of expected inflation, proxied by the U. of Michigan Index of Consumer Expectations, to momentary policy shocks. The results, in the last row of Figure 5, show that the expectation measure is more responsive in the post-1984Q1 period. This is especially true for the house prices, as documented by Case and Shiller (2003) [15] who argue that the expectations play an important role on the user costs and decision about housing spending. This indicates that the expectation channel is consistent with larger responsiveness in the post-1984Q1 period than in the pre-1979Q3 period.

In short, our findings in regard to time-varying impact of monetary policy on asset prices appear to support the balance sheet channel and expectation channel.

Figure 5: Impulse responses of Spread, Credits and Expectation Over Two Sample Periods
Notes. The left panel presents impulse responses of spread, credits and expectation to a contractionary monetary policy shock in the pre-1979Q3 period while the middle panel shows the impulse responses in the post-1984Q1 period. The right panel calculated the difference in impulse responses

5.4 Time-varying impacts across business cycles

Figure 6 compares the impulse responses of asset prices to a contractionary monetary policy shock for the recessionary periods and non-recessionary periods. Overall our results suggest the effects are nonlinear across business cycles. The right panel shows that effects of monetary policy are significantly larger for recessionary periods.

Evidence on whether the stock price's reaction to macroeconomic news depends on the state of economy is mixed. For instance, Boyd et al. (2005) [11] demonstrate that the reaction of stock price to unemployment news differs during phases of business cycles and

the difference is accounted for by the equity premium and growth expectation. On the other hand, Andersen et al. (2007) [1] conclude that the responses of the stock market to monetary are not state dependent.

We add to this literature by using a time-varying FAVAR which includes a large-scale data series that are mostly not included in Andersen et al. (2007) [1]. This could help alleviate the mismatch between the large information set used by economic agents and the information set spanned by the variables in the small-scale model. Our evidence shows that the reaction of stock prices to monetary policy are stronger during the recessionary periods. Our results hold if we measure the difference in impulse responses across financial crisis ¹⁶.

Theoretically, our results are consistent with the predictions of financial accelerator theory (Bernanke and Gertler, 1989 [3] and Bernanke, Gertler and Gilchrist, 1999 [6]) which argues that informational frictions are largest and therefore higher cost of external finance in the recessionary periods. This could reduce the firm's investment demand and economic activities. Furthermore, financial intermediaries, such as banks, may choose to reduce the supply of the credit by tightening the credit standard ahead of the recession which makes the firms even harder to get alternative sources of credit. As a result, adverse macroeconomic shocks have larger effects on firm's performance when the economy is in recessionary periods and when the credit market is tight.

5.5 Time-varying transmission of supply and demand shocks

Although our focus in this paper is to investigate the changes in effects of monetary policy shock on asset prices, our model also allows identifying two additional shocks, which is one of advantages over the recursive identification scheme.

Figure 7 presents the impulse response functions of asset prices to a positive demand shock, normalized to increase the real GDP by 1 percent on impact. The impact responses of stock price are positive or ambiguous indicating the short-run earnings channel play a

¹⁶We define financial crisis as by Lopez-Salido and Nelson (2010) [31] plus two years (1987 and 2001) of stock market crashes and Global Financial Crisis (2008-2009)

Figure 6: Impulse responses of Asset Prices Across Business Cycles

Notes. The left panel presents the average impulse responses of asset prices to a contractionary monetary policy shock for the non-recession periods while the middle panel shows the impulse responses for the recession periods. Recessionary periods are defined by NBER. The right panel calculated the difference in impulse responses.

more import role than the increased discount rate caused by concomitant increase in the interest rate. In response to the positive demand shock, there is a temporary increase in interest rate, house prices and oil prices. As to the effective nominal exchange rate, the effects of a positive demand shock are negative caused by rising general price level. In terms of time variations, the transmission of demand shocks is relatively less time varying for stock prices and government bond yield, attested by the approximately even distribution of impulse response in the last column, while the rest seem to be more responsive for second part of the sample.

The impulse responses of asset prices to a negative supply shock can be found in Figure 8, normalized to increase CPI by 1 percent on impact. Except the stock prices, all other asset prices are becoming more responsive over time. This can be easily observed by from Figure 9 which portraits the impact impulse response of asset prices to the negative supply shock.

Figure 7: Impulse Responses of Asset Prices to a Positive Demand Shock

Notes. The left panel is the median impulse response of asset prices within 20 quarters across sample period. The middle two panels present the impulse response for two representative period, 1975Q1 and 2008 Q1, respectively. The right panel shows the joint distribution of impulse responses on impact along with 45 degree line.

Figure 8: Impulse Responses of Asset Prices to a Negative Supply Shock

Notes. The left panel is the median impulse response of asset prices within 20 quarters across sample period. The middle two panels present the impulse response for two representative period, 1975Q1 and 2008 Q1, respectively. The right panel shows the joint distribution of impulse responses on impact along with 45 degree line.

Figure 9: The Impact Responses of Asset Prices to A Negative Supply Shock

Notes. This figure presents the time-varying impulse responses of asset prices on impact to a contractionary supply shock, normalized to increase CPI by 1 percent.

5.6 Quantitative importance of shocks

Impulse responses are used to trace out the effects of an monetary policy shock on the asset prices in the TVP-FAVAR model while the the forecast error variance decomposition exhibits the relatively important different shocks have been on average for each variable. Allowing the evolution of coefficients and stochastic volatility in our framework, we can investigate the time-variation in relative importance of each shock.

Figure 10 displays the evolution of the median contribution of each shock to the forecast

error variance after 20 quarters for asset prices of interest¹⁷. It is clear that the contribution of monetary policy shock exhibits the time variation and how our model captures the important role in the most recent financial crisis, with monetary policy shock contributing around 40% to the forecast error variance of stock prices, government bond yield and effective exchange rate and around 20% to house prices and oil prices. In terms of time variation, it seems that the monetary policy becomes more critical to explain the forecast error variance of asset prices over time.

As to the rest of two shocks, the demand shock tends to be important in the first half of sample and less important in the later part, especially in most recent times. On the contrary, the supply shock plays a much more significant role to explain the forecast error variance of asset prices with fraction ranging from 60-80 percent in recent times for most asset prices.

Figure A5, A6 and A7 in Appendix provides more evidence about the relative importance of the monetary shock, demand shock and supply shocks. These estimates indicate that demand shocks have become a less important source of asset price movements in recent years while monetary policy shocks and supply shocks account for the paramount variances in asset prices. This evidence is consistent with the empirical results of Ellis et al. (2014)[20].

6 Sensitivity analysis

In our main results, I use two factors to capture the information included in macroeconomic series. As a robust check, I increase the number of factors to three. Figure A2 reports the impulse response functions for the specification including three factors. The figure demonstrates that the qualitative and quantitative conclusions on the effects of monetary policy on asset prices are not altered.

In our second robust check, we use the Cholesky decomposition to identify the monetary shock. We have shown the advantages of employing sign restrictions over Cholesky decomposition. But the structure of measurement equation allows asset prices to respond

¹⁷For purpose consistency, one can view CPI as measure of the return of cash.

Figure 10: Forecast Error Variance Decomposition of Asset Prices

Notes. The figure plots median of contribution of monetary policy shocks, demand shocks and supply shocks to the forecast error variance of asset prices after 20 quarters. The shaded areas correspond to: black-monetary policy shocks, light grey-demand shocks and dark grey-supply shocks.

contemporaneously to the monetary policy shock when we set asset prices as 'fast-moving' variables as in Bernanke et al (2005) [5] and the contemporaneous component could be accounted for by factor loading. Figure A6 shows the impulse response functions of asset prices using Cholesky decomposition.

We then proceed to check whether our results are robust to alternative priors. Instead of using OLS estimates of training sample as priors, we use non-informative priors in this section. Figure A3 shows the results with new priors.

Lastly, our results regarding the different effects of monetary policy across business cycles also hold when we use financial crisis periods. The financial crisis periods are defined as

Lopez-Salido and Nelson (2010) [31] plus two years (1987 and 2001) of stock market crashes and Global Financial Crisis (2008 - 2009). The empirical results are reported in Figure A4.

7 Concluding remarks

It is of importance to properly estimate the relationship between monetary policy shocks and asset prices in a time-varying environment where structural changes are not seldom detected. This paper provides the evidence on the contribution of monetary policy to the structural changes in asset prices in the US over the last 50 years. Employing sign restrictions in a time-varying FAVAR framework, we contribute the literature by quantitatively assessing the role of monetary policy shocks in asset prices.

Our paper uncovers several important facts. Firstly, both the stochastic volatility and transmission mechanism of monetary policy shock exhibit time variations over the sample. In line with Canova and Gambetti (2009) [12] and Sims and Zha (2006)[43], the variance of monetary policy shock reached the peak in 1980s and then declined considerably afterward. The asset prices are becoming more responsive in recent times which could potentially make monetary policy more effective. This is consistent with findings by Canova and Gambetti (2009)[12] but in contrast with Paul (2017)[37] who documents the time-varying impacts of monetary policy on house prices and stock prices using monetary policy surprise in a small-scale time-varying VAR. The time variations in the effects of monetary policy on asset prices are also documented across business cycles. Overall, the time-varying impacts of monetary policy on asset prices are consistent the balance sheet channel and expectation channel of the monetary policy. Though the time variation responsiveness of demand shocks is less apparent, the similar pattern could also be found for supply shocks. Secondly, the relative importance of monetary policy shocks and supply shocks increase over time in sample period. The finding chimes with Ellis et al (2014)[20] who also documents the increasingly important role of the supply shock in driving the movements in UK economy. In contrast,

demand shocks becomes less important driver of the most asset price movements in the sample.

Our results suggest that the time variation in the transmission of main macro shocks to asset prices plays a non-negligible role. Taking into account such links within a stochastic, dynamic and general-equilibrium model could uncover fruitful results that might provide more insights on the financial channels through which the macro shocks interact with the real economy.

Acknowledgement

Appendix

Estimation of TVP-VAR

To estimate the TVP-FAVAR model described in Section 4, we first initialize the factors as the principal components of all macroeconomics data series. Then the time-varying VAR model is firstly simulated following the algorithm developed by Primiceri (2005) [39] and Del Negro and Primiceri (2015)[19]. Following Carter and Kohn (1994)[14], the density of β_t can be factored as:

$$p(\beta^T|Y^T, A^T, H^T, V) = p(\beta_T, |Y^T, A^T, H^T, V) \sum_{i=1}^n p(\beta_t|\beta_{t+1}, Y^T, A^T, H^T, V)$$

The conditional mean and variance of $(\beta_t|\beta_{t+1}, Y^T, A^T, H^T, V)$ are denoted with $\beta_{t|t+1}$ and $P_{t|t+1}$ which can be computed by using Kalman filter and Kalman smoother for the state space model consisting of (4) and (5).

Having drawn the coefficients, next we draw covariance matrix A . Given the draw of the VAR coefficients and other initial parameters, equation (4) could be written as

$$A_t(Y_t - Z_t'\beta_t) = A_t\hat{Y}_t = H_t\epsilon_t$$

Though further manipulation, the $i+1$ -th can be written as

$$\hat{Y}_{i+1,t} = -\hat{Y}_{[1,i]}\alpha_{i,t} + h_{i,t}\epsilon_{i+1,t}$$

where $h_{i,t}$ and $\epsilon_{i,t}$ are the i -th elements of h_t and ϵ_t respectively and $\hat{Y}_{[1,i]} = [\hat{Y}_{1,t}, \dots, \hat{Y}_{i,t}]$. In combination of equation (6), we have another state space model that can be calculated by using Kalman filter and smoother in the same as sampling the coefficients β_t .

To draw volatility states, we firstly convert the equation $A_t\hat{Y}_t = Y_t^* = H_t\epsilon_t$ ¹⁸ into linear

¹⁸Note that conditional on draws of A , now the left hand side is observable. So we make it equal to y_t^* .

equations by squaring and taking logarithms of each element. In combination of equation (7), we get the following state space model:

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\hat{Y}_t^2 + 0.001) &= 2\ln h_t + \zeta_t \\ \ln h_t &= \ln h_{t-1} + \kappa_t \end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta_t = \log(\epsilon_t^2)$. We employ the method in Kim et al. (1998)[25] to convert the state space model, where the innovation term is not normally distributed¹⁹, into Gaussian system. To do this, we use the mixture of 7 Normals to approximate the distribution of innovation term in measurement equation. Defining an indicator matrix $s^T = [s_1, \dots, s_T]'$ that tells information about which member of the mixture of normal has been selected. Conditional s^T, β^T, A^T and V , the state space could be applied to Carter and Kohn (1994) [14] algorithm where the conditional mean and variance are obtained from kalman filter and Kalman smoother. Then the hyperparameters from the specified inverse-Wishart distributions respectively.

The factor loadings and the corresponding variances are then sampled given the macroeconomic series data and federal funds rate based on the standard Bayesian procedure for regressions. Lastly, factors are sampled based on the methods employed in Bernanke et al. (2005) [5] and Kim and Nelson (1999) [25] which follows a same strategy for a linear Gaussian state space model as sampling coefficients of time-varying VAR. To summarize, the algorithm proceeds as follows:

1. Initialize the values of factors using principal component and all the parameters A^T, H^T, s^T and V .
2. Sample β^T from $p(\beta^T|Y^T, A^T, H^T, V)$.
3. Sample A^T from $p(A^T|Y^T, \beta^T, H^T, V)$.
4. Sample H^T from $p(H^T|Y^T, A^T, \beta^T, V, s^T)$.
5. Sample s^T from $p(s^T|Y^T, A^T, H^T, V)$.
6. Sample hyperparameters V by separately sampling Q, S and Z .
7. Given initial values of factors and draw of VAR parameters, sample factor loadings λ and ψ and variances from a normal and inverse gamma distribution, respectively
8. Sample factors using the method employed in Bernanke et al. (2005) [5] and Kim and Nelson (1999) [25].
9. Repeat 2-8.

We run 110,000 replications of the Gibbs sampler and discard the first 100,000 as "burn-in". To reduce the autocorrelation, we only keep every tenth draw of the posterior of parameters. As in Primiceri (2005) [39], we check the convergence of the algorithm by computing the inefficiency factors using the inverse of the relative numerical efficiency measure (RNE):

$$RNE = (2\pi)^{-1} \frac{1}{S(0)} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} S(\omega) d\omega \quad (10)$$

where $S(\omega)$ is the spectral density of the retained draws for the parameters of interest at frequency ω .

Figure A1 plots the inefficiency factors for the time-varying coefficients (β_t), off-diagonal elements of contemporaneous matrix (A_t) and stochastic volatilities (H_t) in the transition

¹⁹As noted in Primiceri (2005) [39], the innovation is distributed as $\log\chi^2(1)$.

equation. The graph shows that the values of inefficiency factors are all less than 0.6, far below the value of 20^{20} , and therefore indicates that the autocorrelation in the sequence draws is low.

Figure A1: Inefficiency factors of MCMC algorithm

Dataset

In this section, we present the full list of data series as well as their mnemonic names. All macroeconomic data series are collected from Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis except that PMI, PMNO, PMDEL, PMNV, MOCMQ and MSONDQ are from Datastream. House price index and S&P price index are gathered from Robert Shiller's website.

²⁰Primerici (2005) pointed out the values of inefficiency factors below 20 are satisfactory for an MCMC algorithm to be convergent.

Figure A2: Impulse responses of Asset Prices for 3 Factors in TVP-FAVAR

Figure A3: Impulse responses of Asset Prices for Non-informative Priors in TVP-FAVAR

Figure A4: Impulse responses of Asset Prices Over Financial Crisis Periods

Notes. The left panel presents impulse responses of asset prices to a contractionary monetary policy shock for the non-financial crisis periods while the middle panel shows the impulse responses for the financial crisis periods. The right panel calculated the difference in impulse responses. Financial crisis periods are defined similar to Lopez-Salido and Nelson (2010)[31]

Figure A5: Median of Contribution of Monetary Policy Shocks to the Forecast Error Variance of Asset Prices

Figure A6: Median of Contribution of Demand Shocks to the Forecast Error Variance of Asset Prices

Figure A7: Median of Contribution of Supply Shocks to the Forecast Error Variance of Asset Prices

1	CBI	Change in Private Inventories
2	GDPC96	Real Gross Domestic Product
3	FINSLC96	Real Final Sales of Domestic Product, 3 Decimal
4	CIVA	Corporate Inventory Valuation Adjustment
5	CP	Corporate Profits After Tax
6	CNCF	Corporate Net Cash Flow
7	GDPCTPI	Gross Domestic Product: Chain-type Price Index
8	FPI	Fixed Private Investment
9	GSAVE	Gross Saving
10	PRFI	Private Residential Fixed Investment
11	CMDEBT	House Hold and Nonprofit Organization Liability Level
12	INDPRO	Industrial Production Index
13	NAPM	ISM Manufacturing: PMI Composite Index
14	HCOMPBS	Compensation Per Hour in Business Sector
15	HOABS	Business Sector: Hours of All Persons
16	RCPHBS	Business Sector: Real Compensation Per Hour
17	ULCBS	Business Sector: Unit Labor Cost
18	COMPNFB	Nonfarm Business Sector: Compensation Per Hour
19	HOANBS	Nonfarm Business Sector: Hours of All Persons
20	COMPRNFB	Nonfarm Bus. Sector: Real Compensation Per Hour
21	ULCNFB	Nonfarm Business Sector: Unit Labor Cost
22	UEMPLT5	Civilians Unemployed - Less Than 5 Weeks
23	UEMP5TO14	Civilian Unemployed for 5-14 Weeks
24	UEMP15OV	Civilians Unemployed - 15 Weeks & Over
25	UEMP15T26	Civilians Unemployed for 15-26 Weeks
26	UEMP27OV	Civilians Unemployed for 27 Weeks and Over
27	NDMANEMP	All Employees: Nondurable Goods Manufacturing
28	MANEMP	Employees on Nonfarm Payrolls: Manufacturing
29	SRVPRD	All Employees: Service-Providing Industries
30	USTPU	All Employees: Trade, Transportation & Utilities
31	USWTRADE	All Employees: Wholesale Trade
32	USTRADE	All Employees: Retail Trade
33	USFIRE	All Employees: Financial Activities

34	USEHS	All Employees: Education & Health Services
35	USPBS	All Employees: Professional & Business Services
36	USINFO	All Employees: Information Services
37	USSERV	All Employees: Other Services
38	USPRIV	All Employees: Total Private Industries
39	USGOVT	All Employees: Government
40	USLAH	All Employees: Leisure and Hospitality
41	AHECONS	Average Hourly Earnings: Construction
42	AHEMAN	Average Hourly Earnings: Manufacturing
43	AHETPI	Average Hourly Earnings of Production and Nonsupervisory Employees: Total Private
44	AWOTMAN	Average Weekly Hours: Overtime: Manufacturing
45	AWHMAN	Average Weekly Hours: Manufacturing
46	HOUST	Housing Starts: Total: New Privately Owned Housing Units Started
47	HOUSTNE	Housing Starts in Northeast Census Region
48	HOUSTMW	Housing Starts in Midwest Census Region
49	HOUSTS	Housing Starts: Total: New Privately Owned Housing Units Started
50	HOUSTW	Housing Starts in West Census Region
51	HOUST1F	Privately Owned Housing Starts: 1-Unit Structures
52	PERMIT	New Private Housing Units Authorized by Building Permit
53	NONREVSL	Total Non-revolving Credit Outstanding
54	USGSEC	U.S. Government Securities at All Commercial Banks
55	OTHSEC	Other Securities at All Commercial Banks
56	TOTALSL	Total Consumer Credit Outstanding
57	BUSLOANS	Commercial and Industrial Loans at All Commercial Banks
58	CONSUMER	Consumer (Individual) Loans at All Commercial Banks
59	LOANS	Total Loans and Leases at Commercial Banks
60	LOANINV	Bank Credit at All Commercial Banks
61	INVEST	Total Investments at All Commercial Banks
62	REALLN	Real Estate Loans at All Commercial Banks
63	BOGAMBSL	Board of Governors Monetary Base, Adjusted for Changes in Reserve Req
64	TRARR	Board of Governors Total Reserves, Adjusted for Changes in Reserve Req.
65	BOGNONBR	Non-Borrowed Reserves of Depository Institutions
66	NFORBRES	Net Free or Borrowed Reserves of Depository Institutions
67	M1SL	M1 Money Stock

68	CURRSL	Currency Component of M1
69	CURRDD	Currency Component of M1 Plus Demand Deposits
70	DEMDEPSL	Demand Deposits at Commercial Banks
71	TCDSL	Total Checkable Deposits
72	TB3MS	3-Month Treasury Bill: Secondary Market Rate
73	TB6MS	6-Month Treasury Bill: Secondary Market Rate
74	GS1	1-Year Treasury Constant Maturity Rate
75	GS3	3-Year Treasury Constant Maturity Rate
76	GS5	5-Year Treasury Constant Maturity Rate
77	GS10	10-Year Treasury Constant Maturity Rate
78	MPRIME	Bank Prime Loan Rate
79	AAA	Moody's Seasoned AAA Corporate Bond Yield
80	BAA	Moody's Seasoned BAA Corporate Bond Yield
81	sTB3MS	TB3MS - FEDFUNDS
82	sTB6MS	TB6MS - FEDFUNDS
83	sGS1	GS1 - FEDFUNDS
84	sGS3	GS3 - FEDFUNDS
85	sGS5	GS5 - FEDFUNDS
86	sGS10	GS10 - FEDFUNDS
87	sMPRIME	MPRIME - FEDFUNDS
88	sAAA	AAA - FEDFUNDS
89	sBAA	BAA - FEDFUNDS
90	EXSZUS	Switzerland / U.S. Foreign Exchange Rate
91	EXJPUS	Japan / U.S. Foreign Exchange Rate
92	PPIACO	Producer Price Index: All Commodities
93	PPICRM	Producer Price Index: Crude Materials for Further Proc.
94	PPIFCF	Producer Price Index: Finished Consumer Foods
95	PPIFCG	Producer Price Index: Finished Consumer Goods
96	PFCGEF	Producer Price Index: Finished Consumer Goods Excl. Foods
97	PPIFGS	Producer Price Index: Finished Goods
98	PPICPE	Producer Price Index Finished Goods: Capital Equipment
99	PPIENG	Producer Price Index: Fuels & Related Products & Power
100	PPIIDC	Producer Price Index: Industrial Commodities
101	PPIITM	Producer Price Index: Intermediate Materials

102	CPIAUCSL	Consumer Price Index For All Urban Consumers: All Items
103	CPIUFDSL	Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers: Food
104	CPIENGSL	Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers: Energy
105	CPILEGSL	Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers: All Items Less Energy
106	CPIULFSL	Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers: All Items Less Food
107	CPILFESL	Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers: All Items Less Food and Energy
108	OILPRICE	Spot Oil Price: West Texas Intermediate
109	HHSNTN	U. Of Mich. Index Of Consumer Expectations
110	PMI	Purchasing Manager's Index
111	PMNO	NAPM New Orders Index
112	PMDEL	NAPM Vendor Deliveries Index
113	PMNV	NAPM Inventories Index
114	MOCMQ	New Orders (Net) - Consumer Goods & Materials
115	MSONDQ	New Orders, Nondefense Capital Goods
116	SP500	S&P 500 Price Index
117	HPRICE	House Price Index
118	FEDFUNDS	Effective Federal Funds Rate

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